

Studies in Indigoid Dyes.

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In two previous papers (Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 10, 679; Guha and Basu-Mallik, *ibid.*, 1934, 11, 395) it has been shown that 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (Auwers and Arndt, *Ber.*, 1909, 42, 551) interacts very readily with acenaphthenequinone, isatin and their various derivatives and also phenanthraquinone yielding beautiful indigoid vat dyes which impart a deeper shade on wool as well as on cotton than those of the corresponding compounds obtained from 3-hydroxythionaphthene (Bezdzik and Friedlander, *Monatsh.*, 1908, 29, 376, 386; E.P. 6490-07; G.P. appl. G 25209; Dutt, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 99; Guha, *ibid.*, 1932, 9, 423).

In the present paper the action of 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene has been investigated on various aldehydes with the object of studying if the resulting products would possess any value as vat dyes. Benzylidene-2(5-methyl)-thionaphthene has been prepared and described by Auwers and Arndt (*loc. cit.*) but no dyeing property appears to have been examined and recorded. With the exception of this no other dyestuff has been obtained from 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene by condensation with aliphatic or aromatic aldehydes. The following aldehydes have, therefore, been condensed with 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene and the corresponding dyestuffs obtained: glyoxal, *p*-dimethylamino-, *m*-amino-, *p*-nitro-, *m*-nitro-, *p*-chloro-, *p*-methoxy-, *p*-hydroxy-, *m*-hydroxy-, *p*-methyl-, *m*-methoxy-*p*-hydroxybenzaldehyde, piperonal, protocatechuic and cinnamic aldehydes.

It has been found that the methylhydroxythionaphthene reacts quite easily with the above mentioned aldehydes. The condensation products are all coloured solids. They are characterised by their marked ability to crystallise so that they are quite suitable for the identification of aldehydes. In the case of nitro-, amino-, and hydroxybenzylidene-2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthenes it has been observed that the compounds having NO₂, NH₂ or OH group in the *meta* position to the benzylidene part of the molecule are lighter in shade than the corresponding substances having the same group in the *para* position. All these newly prepared substances dissolve in strong

sulphuric acid with a characteristic colour and the original substances are reprecipitated by the addition of water in a finely divided condition suitable for dyeing wool from an acid bath. The shades on wool are uniformly and fully developed. The attempt to develop these colours on cotton from an alkaline hydrosulphite vat, except in the case of bis-2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo which gave very satisfactory result, was rather disappointing. Generally speaking, they offered great resistance to be converted easily into soluble vats. The shades obtained on cotton although fairly uniform, are invariably very much lighter than those of the original substances. Although repeatedly tried, the cinnamylidene compound could not, however, be developed on cotton.

Lastly, aceanthraquinone (Liebermann and Zsuffa, *Ber.*, 1911, 44, 209) and the methylhydroxythionaphthene have yielded in boiling glacial acetic acid an indigoid dye, the dyeing properties of which have been compared with 2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene-acenaphthylene-indigo (Guha, *loc. cit.*).

EXPERIMENTAL.

bis-2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-ethylene-indigo.

An aqueous solution of glyoxal sodium bisulphite (0.284 g. in 5 c.c. of water) was added to a solution of 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) and the mixture treated with concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.) and shaken well. After 1½ hours' heating deep red fine silky needles separated which were filtered hot, washed with alcohol and then with hot water and crystallised from pyridine or nitrobenzene in clusters of dark red needles not melting below 300°. The dye is soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline, xylene; difficultly soluble in amyl alcohol, chloroform, toluene; sparingly soluble in methyl alcohol, acetone; insoluble in petroleum ether, strong ammonia and caustic alkalis. It dissolves in strong sulphuric acid with a deep green colour and dyes wool in dark red shades; and cotton is dyed in beautiful violet-red

shade from a deep yellow vat. (Found: S, 18.6. $C_{20}H_{14}O_2S_2$ requires S, 18.28 per cent).

4'-Dimethylaminobenzylidene-2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene.

A solution of 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) and *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (0.298 g.) in hot absolute alcohol (10 c.c.) on treatment with concentrated hydrochloric acid (1 c.c.) turned deep reddish brown (almost red). It was heated on the water-bath for 15 minutes and cooled under a stream of water when the hydrochloride of the condensation product separated in yellow diamond-shaped crystals. It was collected, washed with dilute alcohol (1:1) when the free base separated, which was collected, washed well with hot water and crystallised from dilute acetic acid or pyridine in shining red prisms, m.p. 198-99°. It is soluble in acetic acid, chloroform, methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, amyl alcohol, pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline, benzene, toluene, xylene, acetone, carbon tetrachloride; sparingly soluble in petroleum ether, insoluble in ammonia and caustic alkalis. Strong sulphuric acid dissolves it with a blue colouration. It dyes wool in cinnabar-red shades and cotton in pink colour from faintly red vat. (Found: N, 4.98. $C_{18}H_{17}ONS$ requires N, 4.74 per cent).

3'-Aminobenzylidene-2-(5-methyl)-thionaphthene.—The hydrochloride separated as yellow shining plates on heating for 15 minutes the reddish brown solution obtained by adding methylhydroxythionaphthene (0.656 g.) in 8 c.c. of boiling alcohol to *m*-aminobenzaldehyde (0.484 g.) in a mixture of boiling alcohol (30 c.c.) and concentrated hydrochloric acid (5 c.c.). It was collected and boiled with 2*N*-caustic soda, filtered hot and washed with hot water and crystallised from dilute pyridine in brownish yellow silky needles, m.p. 157°. The substance gives a violet-blue solution in strong sulphuric acid and dyes wool in deep yellow shades from an acid bath and cotton in yellow shades from an alkaline faintly yellow vat. All other properties resemble those of the preceding compound. (Found: N, 5.58. $C_{16}H_{13}ONS$ requires N, 5.24 per cent).

The compounds described in Table I were prepared by taking molecular quantities of 5-methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene and the corresponding aldehyde in hot absolute alcohol and adding 2-3 c.c. of concentrated hydrochloric acid. The product separated at once from the boiling solution. It was collected and crystallised from dilute

acetic acid except where otherwise mentioned. They are soluble in nitrobenzene, aniline, pyridine, amyl alcohol, acetic acid and all of them except the hydroxy compounds are insoluble in strong ammonia and caustic alkalis.

2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene-1'-aceanthrylene-indigo.

5-Methyl-3-hydroxythionaphthene (0.328 g.) was added to a solution of aceanthraquinone (0.464 g.) in boiling acetic acid (40 c.c.) and heated for a while. The whole solution turned deep reddish brown and on the addition of concentrated hydrochloric acid (2 c.c.) a deep red crystalline substance was at once precipitated. The mixture was heated to boiling for 15 minutes and filtered hot, the product washed well with glacial acetic acid and boiled water, dried and crystallised from xylene or nitrobenzene in fine clusters of deep red needles, m.p. above 310°, on further heating it volatilises evolving red vapours. It is soluble in pyridine, nitrobenzene, aniline, xylene; difficultly soluble in amyl alcohol, benzene, toluene, chloroform; sparingly soluble in alcohol, petroleum ether; moderately soluble in acetic acid, acetone, carbon tetrachloride. The solution in concentrated sulphuric acid is yellowish green. It dyes wool in orange-brown shades from an acid bath and cotton in light red ochre colour from a yellow vat. (Found: S, 8.45. $C_{25}H_{14}O_2S$ requires S, 8.46 per cent).

TABLE I.

B = Benzylidene; C = Cinnamylidene; P = Piperonylidene; M = 2-(5-Methyl)-thionaphthene.

Name and formula.	M.p.	Colour in strong H_2SO_4	Shade on wool from acid bath.	Shade on cotton of vat in brackets.	Colour Analysis. Found. Calc.	Remarks.
4'-Nitro-BM $C_{16}H_{11}O_2NS$	264°	Greenish blue	Orange-yellow	Light orange (deep orange-red)	N, 5.03 4.71	Orange-red rectangles from glacial acetic acid, soluble in chloroform, benzene, toluene, xylene; moderately soluble in CCl_4 , acetone; sparingly soluble in ethyl alcohol, petroleum ether.
3'-Nitro-BM $C_{16}H_{11}O_2NS$	233°	Blue	Yellow	Yellow (light yellow)	N, 4.99 4.71	Yellow silky rectangles from acetic acid; solubilities same as in the previous compound.
4'-Chloro-BM $C_{16}H_{11}O$ ClS	178°	Reddish brown	Yellow	Faint yellow (faint greenish yellow)	Cl, 12.54 12.38	Bright yellow rectangles from alcohol, soluble in $CHCl_3$, alcohol, benzene, xylene, acetone. CCl_4 ; sparingly in petroleum ether.
4'-Methoxy-BM $C_{17}H_{14}O_2S$	157°	Deep red	Bright yellow	Yellow (faint yellow)	S, 11.08 11.34	Bright yellow needles, moderately soluble in petroleum ether; other properties resemble the preceding compound.
4'-Hydroxy-BM $C_{16}H_{10}O_2S$	252°	Brownish red	Deep and bright yellow.	Yellow (colourless)	12.27 11.94	Light brownish yellow silky needles, soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone, toluene, xylene; difficultly soluble in $CHCl_3$ and benzene.
3'-Hydroxy-BM (separated on cooling) $C_{16}H_{12}O_2S$	200°	"	Deep yellow	Faint yellow (colourless)	12.20 11.94	Deep yellow needles, soluble in alcohol, chloroform, benzene, toluene, xylene, difficultly in CCl_4 .

Name and formula.	M.p.	Colour in strong H_2SO_4 .	Shade on wool from acid bath.	Shade on cotton of vat in brackets.	Colour.	Analysis.	Remarks.
						Found. Calc.	
4'-Methyl-BM. (Separated on cooling) $C_{17}H_{14}OS$	169°	Brownish red	Yellow	Yellow (faint yellow)	Yellow (faint yellow)	S, 12.09 12.03	Yellow clusters of needles from glacial acetic acid, soluble in acetone, $CHCl_3$, CCl_4 , benzene, toluene, xylene, petroleum ether; difficultly in methyl and ethyl alcohol.
3'-Methoxy-4'-hydroxy-BM (Do.) $C_{17}H_{14}O_3S$	194°	Deep red	Deep yellow	Yellowish brown (pinkish red).	Yellowish brown (pinkish red).	10.6 10.73	Deep yellow needles, soluble in alcohol, $CHCl_3$, benzene xylene, acetone, CCl_4 .
3':4'-Dihydroxy-BM. $C_{16}H_{12}O_3S$	248°	"	Brownish yellow	Light reddish brown (light blue)	Light reddish brown (light blue)	11.46 11.26	Light brown shining rectangles, soluble in methyl alcohol, ethyl alcohol, acetone; moderately in $CHCl_3$, benzene, xylene; insoluble in petroleum ether.
P M $C_{17}H_{12}O_3S$	231°	Purple	Deep yellow	Dull faint yellow (faint yellow)	Dull faint yellow (faint yellow)	11.05 10.81	Deep yellow needles, soluble in acetone, $CHCl_3$, benzene; difficultly in alcohol; sparingly in petroleum ether.
C M $C_{18}H_{14}OS$	184°	Violet-red	Dull orange-yellow.			11.26 11.61	Orange-yellow small needles, soluble in acetone, $CHCl_3$, benzene xylene, alcohol; sparingly in petroleum ether.
BM (cf. Auwers & Arndt, loc.cit.) $C_{18}H_{12}OS$	147°	Brownish red	Yellow	Light yellow (faint yellow)	Light yellow (faint yellow)	12.49 12.69	Yellow shining rectangles, soluble in acetone, CCl_4 , methyl alcohol, benzene, toluene, xylene; moderately soluble in petroleum ether.

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